

Periodic MPC for glucose control in Type 1 Diabetes¹

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Abstract: Glucose control in Type 1 Diabetes (T1D) is a challenging task due to several factors among which intra- and inter-patient variability play a key role. This work introduces a Periodic Multiple Model Predictor (PeMMP) integrated in a Periodic Model Predictive Control (PeMPC) to enhance glucose regulation. The PeMMP is able to account for time-varying dynamics by switching smoothly between multiple models. In a case study including a single patient of the UVA/Padova simulator, the PeMMP improves prediction accuracy compared to the traditional Daily Model Predictor (DMP) (fitting index 81.9% vs 39.7%). These more accurate predictions lead to an improvement in control performances when exploited in a PeMPC especially in the postprandial periods increasing the time in range (93.45% to 96.31%) and decreasing hypoglycemia (1.42% to 0%) and hypo treatments (10 to 0). These results highlight PeMPC as a promising approach for better managing T1D, its use on the entire in silico population is currently under study.

Keywords: Artificial pancreas, Diabetes, Time-varying systems, Model Predictive Control, Control of physiological systems

1. INTRODUCTION

Type 1 Diabetes (T1D) is an autoimmune disease characterized by high Blood Glucose (BG) levels, also known as hyperglycemia ($BG > 180$ [mg/dl]). To manage this condition, patients require carefully regulated insulin therapy, as excessive insulin can lead to hypoglycemia ($BG < 70$ [mg/dl]). The primary goal for individuals with T1D is to maintain their glucose levels within the safe range of 70 - 180 [mg/dl]. The most advanced treatment for T1D is the Artificial Pancreas (AP), a closed-loop system consisting of a Continuous Glucose Monitor (CGM), a subcutaneous (sc) insulin pump, and a control algorithm (Cobelli et al. (2011); Thabit and Hovorka (2016)). Among the various control strategies, Model Predictive Control (MPC) has emerged as one of the most promising techniques for glucose regulation. The core of MPC is a dynamic model that predicts the patient's future BG levels, making the accuracy of these predictions a key point to achieve optimal control performance. The identification of this model is not a trivial task since it should take into account the inter- and intra-patient variability among in-

dividuals with T1D. The use of average population models capable of generalizing T1D population dynamics, tested on the UVA/Padova metabolic simulator (Visentin et al. (2014)), has shown promising but limited performance in terms of glucose control (Toffanin and Magni (2023a,b)). To achieve better results, the model must closely match the specific patient dynamics, highlighting the necessity of using personalized models (Toffanin et al. (2018)). These models have demonstrated improved prediction accuracy; however, some patients still experienced hypoglycemia events when the MPC uses a single Daily Model Predictor (DMP). This issue, as highlighted by the authors, could be attributed to intra-day variability, i.e. changes in patient dynamics throughout the day, due for example to insulin sensitivity, that can't be captured by a unique time-invariant model. To accommodate patients with high insulin sensitivity variability, this work presents an improved version of the Multiple Model Predictor (MMP) introduced in Toffanin et al. (2019). The enhancement employs a clinically-based cost function to asymmetrically weight hypoglycemia, hyperglycemia, and normoglycemia during the identification process. Furthermore, a smooth switching mechanism between multiple models is used to increase BG prediction accuracy giving rise to a Periodic MMP (PeMMP). Periodic physiological models applied in an MPC were considered in Abuin et al. (2022), although with promising results, no periodic control law were considered by the authors. In this work the PeMMP is used to design a Periodic MPC (PeMPC) and a periodic Kalman

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filter enabling the controller to consider recurring patterns in physiological states such as circadian rhythms in insulin sensitivity (Bittanti, Sergio and Colaneri, Patrizio and De Nicolao, Giuseppe (1991); Assimakis and Adam (2009)). By leveraging periodic control theory, the MPC can anticipate and adapt its action to these variations, thus improving glucose regulation. The proposed approach is tested, as case study, on a virtual patient of the UVA/Padova simulator, which obtained poor glucose control with the MPC proposed in Toffanin and Magni (2023a) that is equipped with a Daily model (DMPC). The main contributions of this work are: (i) an innovative identification approach to combine multiple personalized patient models into an PeMMP, effectively addressing glucose variations throughout the day by dynamically switching between models tailored to different daily periods; (ii) the integration of the PeMMP into a PeMPC and a periodic Kalman filter leveraging periodic control techniques to enhance glucose regulation; this solution offers a robust and adaptive approach to manage intra-day glucose variability in T1D patients, improving both prediction and control outcomes.

The paper is structured as follows: Section 2 describes the new identification procedure to obtain the PeMMP, Section 3 introduces and details the implementation of the PeMPC to take into account a time-varying model. Section 4 presents the performance evaluation of the proposed approach, and Section 5 provides the conclusions.

2. MODEL IDENTIFICATION PROCEDURE

This section outlines a newly developed approach for identifying a patient's personalized PeMMP. The process begins with the identification of individual models for specific periods of the day. These models are then combined using a soft-switching mechanism to develop the PeMMP.

The model identification of patient tailored models is a challenging task due to patient's variability. Additionally, realistic data often include synchronous meals and insulin administration (treated meals), further complicating the model identification process. A promising approach is the Impulse Response (IR) identification (Toffanin et al. (2019)), which has demonstrated promising results both in vivo and in silico. This approach consists in identifying two Transfer Functions (TFs), $G_i(s)$ and $G_d(s)$ such that the Laplace transform of the overall model can be written as:

$$\widehat{G}(s) = G_i(s)I(s) + G_d(s)D(s)$$

where $G_i(s)$ and $G_d(s)$ represent the TFs corresponding to the effects of insulin and meals, respectively. The terms $I(s)$, $D(s)$ and $\widehat{G}(s)$ denote the Laplace transforms of the differential insulin, meals and glucose predicted by the model with respect to their steady state values respectively. Due to the impossibility of performing extensive and potentially dangerous experiments on human subjects, the identification technique is divided into two steps.

Step 1: Linear Average Model. It is entirely developed on the average in silico patient (Av) of the UVA/Padova simulator using two scenarios with highly exciting input data that could not be applied to real patients. Both scenarios lasted one day: the first scenario consists of a single meal without any insulin boluses to identify G_d , while the second scenario involves a single insulin bolus

without meal administration to identify G_i . The outputs of this first step are the two TFs $G_i(s)$ and $G_d(s)$ that describe the dynamics of Av . The transfer functions are defined as:

$$G_i(s) = \frac{\mu_i}{(1 + sT_{i1})(1 + sT_{i2})(1 + sT_{i3})(1 + sT_{i4})} \quad (1)$$

$$G_d(s) = \frac{\mu_d}{(1 + sT_{d1})(1 + sT_{d2})(1 + sT_{d3})}$$

where the orders have been selected by a trial and error procedure. The vector θ of the parameters to be identified is: $\theta = [\theta_i \ \theta_d]$

where $\theta_i = [\mu_i \ T_{i1} \ T_{i2} \ T_{i3} \ T_{i4}]$ and $\theta_d = [\mu_d \ T_{d1} \ T_{d2} \ T_{d3}]$. The optimal parameters vector, denoted by θ^{Av} , is obtained through the solution of two independent constrained optimization problems: one to compute the optimal value of θ_i , denoted by θ_i^{Av} , and the other to compute the optimal value of θ_d , denoted by θ_d^{Av} . Both optimization problems aim to minimize the Sum of Squared Residuals (SSR) cost, which is computed as the difference between the glucose (G) measured by CGM and \widehat{G}

$$SSR = \|G(k) - \widehat{G}(k)\|_2^2 \quad (2)$$

with $\|x(k)\|_2$ being the l_2 norm of the signal $x(k)$, namely $\sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^N x(k)^2}$, where N is the number of data points. To ensure system stability, the minimization problems are performed with the constraint of non-negativity of the time constants by adding a barrier function to the SSR. Since the residuals are described by a nonlinear function of the model parameters, an iterative nonlinear least squares algorithm is used. This procedure starts by estimating the gain and the slow time constant of each transfer function, while other time constants are initialized to 1. The gains are set equal to the areas under the curve of the impulse response data and the slow time constant (T_1) is estimated from the final part of these data, assuming that the effects of the faster time constants are negligible in this window.

Step 2: Linear Personalized Model. Starting from the Av model obtained in step 1, the objective of step 2 is to identify a patient personalized model using realistic patient input-output data via a constrained nonlinear optimization procedure. A constrained optimization problem is formulated to optimize the model parameters that minimizes a clinically-based cost function defined by

$$SSR_\eta = \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^N [\eta(k) (\widehat{G}(k) - G(k))]^2} \quad (3)$$

where $\eta(k) = 1 + BGI(G(k))/100$, N denotes the number of CGM samples in the data. The BGI (Kovatchev et al. (2005)) is a metric used to evaluate the clinical risk associated with a specific glucose value. It places greater emphasis on critical situations, such as hypoglycemia and hyperglycemia, by appropriately weighting the deviation from the reference value. The BGI function is asymmetric because hypoglycemia is considered more dangerous than hyperglycemia and it is defined as follows

$$BGI(\cdot) = 10 [1.509 (\ln(\cdot))^{1.084} - \ln(\tilde{y})^{1.084}]^2$$

where \tilde{y} is the target glucose output.

The optimization problem is divided into two parts. In the first part, the parameters θ_i are estimated by keeping

θ_d fixed to the Av values $\theta_{i1}^* = \arg \min_{\theta_i} SSR_{\eta}(\theta_i)$. In the second part, the estimated θ_{i1}^* is set as initial value for θ_i while θ_d is initialized using the clinical gains and time constants acquired from step 1. Both θ_i and θ_d are optimized to obtain the most accurate estimation $\theta^* = \arg \min_{\theta} SSR_{\eta}(\theta)$. The continuous-time model is then discretized using the zero-order hold method, resulting in $G_i(z)$ and $G_d(z)$ with the desired sampling time T_s . More details about this technique can be found in Toffanin et al. (2018).

2.1 Multiple Model Predictor

If the datasets used for the IR techniques span an entire day, the identification process results in a DMP; if the datasets are restricted to a single Day Period (DP), the model is specific to that DP. More accurate models for predicting future glucose can be obtained by combining multiple models identified during different DPs in order to take into account the intra-day variability. Considering three DPs, one for each meal, three Basic Models (BMs) will be identified for Breakfast (B), Lunch (L) and Dinner (D) active during $[t_S^B, t_S^L]$, $[t_S^L, t_S^D]$ and $[t_S^D, t_S^B]$ respectively, as proposed in Toffanin et al. (2019). For each model a minimal state state-space realization is obtained in the form:

$$\begin{aligned} x_f(k+1) &= A_f x_f(k) + B_f u(k) + M_f d(k) \\ y_f(k) &= C_f x(k) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $f = \{B, L, D\}$; $x_f(k) \in \mathbb{R}^{n_f}$ is the state vector whose dimension (n_f) is specific for each model; $u(k) = i(k) - i_b(k) \in \mathbb{R}$ [pmol/Kg] is the difference between the injected insulin (i) and its basal value (i_b) that is a clinically well-known time-varying parameter, note that the insulin level is normalized by patient's body weight; $d(k)$ [mg] represents the meal and $y_f(k) = \hat{G}(k) - G_b \in \mathbb{R}$ [mg/dl] is the difference between the predicted glucose and its basal value (G_b).

Switching Mechanism. To combine these multiple models the approach in Toffanin et al. (2019) involves the model making abrupt transitions from one BM to another at a predefined time frame (hard switch). However, recognizing that a sudden change in dynamics is not physiologically plausible, a new switching method (soft switch) has been introduced in this work. It is important to highlight that, while all models are always operational, only a selected group actively contributes during each interval. For example, during periods that are distant from t_S^B , t_S^L and t_S^D , only the model aligned with the current period is engaged. However, during the switching phase, two models concurrently contribute to the prediction. The involvement of these models is regulated by the signals $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \in [0, 1]$. These signals are used to manage the transitions between the models based on the time of day. During a switch, one signal remains at a constant value of zero, while the other two use ramp signals to ensure a smooth transition between the active models, as reported in Fig. 1 for the lunch transition. The duration of the switching phase can be adjusted by tuning the parameter t_{switch} , which represents half of the total time needed to complete the transition.

The predictor that combines the models for each DP in a soft switching manner is designed as follows:

Fig. 1. This figure illustrates the example of the transition between the BMs B and L: the weight of B prediction gradually decreases, giving more importance to L. The prediction of D is not considered, therefore is put to zero. The duration to complete the switch is $2 \cdot t_{switch}$.

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}(k+1) &= \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}(k) + \mathbf{B}u(k) + \mathbf{M}d(k) \\ y(k) &= \mathbf{C}_j \mathbf{x}(k) \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{x}(k) = [x_B(k), x_L(k), x_D(k)]' \in \mathbb{R}^n$ and

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} A_B & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & A_L & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & A_D \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} B_B \\ B_L \\ B_D \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathbf{M} = \begin{bmatrix} M_B \\ M_L \\ M_D \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

$$\mathbf{C}_j = [\alpha(j)C_B \quad \beta(j)C_L \quad \gamma(j)C_D]$$

where $j := \text{mod}(k, p)$, with mod being an operation that returns the remainder of k divided by p (the number of time steps in one day). The prediction performances of the newly proposed PeMMP will be compared with the state-of-art DMP in Section 4.3. In order to be conservative, BMs are identified exclusively for the DPs where the DMP's performance was inadequate.

3. CONSTRAINED MODEL PREDICTIVE CONTROL

In this section, the PeMPC proposed in this work is formally presented. The MPC introduced in Toffanin and Magni (2023a) employs a discrete-time model to forecast future sc glucose levels (output) as a function of injected insulin (input) and meal intake announced by the patient (disturbance). In this work, the cited MPC is modified to use the PeMMP for prediction. Using the periodic model (5), the PeMPC estimates future BG levels and determines the optimal insulin dose by minimizing the following cost function:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{J}_j(x(k), u(\cdot), k) &= \sum_{i=0}^{N-1} \left(\|y(k+i) - y_0(k+i)\|_q^2 + \right. \\ &\quad \left. + \|u(k+i) - u_0(k+i)\|^2 \right) + \|\mathbf{x}(k+N)\|_{\mathbf{P}_j}^2 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where q is the positive output weight to be tuned, N is the prediction horizon and \mathbf{P}_j is a symmetric positive definite matrix computed by solving the following discrete-time periodic Riccati equation:

$$\mathbf{P}_{j-1} = \mathbf{A}'\mathbf{P}_j\mathbf{A} + q\mathbf{C}_j'\mathbf{C}_j - \mathbf{A}\mathbf{P}_j\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{I}_n + \mathbf{B}\mathbf{P}_j\mathbf{B})^{-1}\mathbf{B}'\mathbf{P}_j\mathbf{A}$$

Additionally, $y_0(k) = \tilde{y}(k) - G_b$ [mg/dl] is the difference between the output reference value \tilde{y} and G_b , and $u_0(k) = \tilde{u}(k) - i_b(k)$ [pmol/Kg] is the difference between the insulin profile's reference value \tilde{u} and $i_b(k)$ normalized with respect to patient's weight.

3.1 Time-varying Kalman filter

The state $\mathbf{x}(k)$ of the model, in general, is not measurable and thus has to be estimated by a KF (see Toffanin and

Magni (2023a)). The KF leverages both the knowledge of the model and past information of insulin injections and meals to estimate the current state, thereby enhancing the accuracy of the optimization process. In order to design the KF, the discrete linear system (5) has to be extended by considering the noise as:

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{x}(k+1) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{x}(k) + \mathbf{B}u(k) + \mathbf{M}d(k) + v_x(k) \\ y(k) = \mathbf{C}_j\mathbf{x}(k) + v_y(k) \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where $v = [v_x \ v_y]'$ is a multivariate zero-mean white Gaussian noise with covariance matrix V and the initial state $x_0 = x(0)$ is assumed to be a zero-mean Gaussian random variable independent of v , where

$$V = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{Q} & 0 \\ 0 & \tilde{R} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \tilde{Q} > 0, \quad \tilde{R} > 0 \quad (9)$$

where \tilde{Q} is the process noise covariance and \tilde{R} the measurement noise covariance. The dynamical system derived from the KF can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{\mathbf{x}}(k+1|k) &= \mathbf{A}\hat{\mathbf{x}}(k|k) + \mathbf{B}u(k) + \mathbf{M}d(k) \\ \hat{\mathbf{x}}(k|k) &= \hat{\mathbf{x}}(k|k-1) + \mathbf{L}_j(y(k) - \mathbf{C}_j\hat{\mathbf{x}}(k|k-1)) \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathbf{L}_j = \tilde{\mathbf{P}}_j\mathbf{C}_j'(\mathbf{C}_j\tilde{\mathbf{P}}_j\mathbf{C}_j' + \tilde{R})^{-1}$ and $\tilde{\mathbf{P}}_j$ is the steady state periodic stabilizing solution with period p of the discrete-time periodic Riccati equation

$$\tilde{\mathbf{P}}_{j+1} = \mathbf{A}\tilde{\mathbf{P}}_j\mathbf{A}' + \tilde{Q} - \mathbf{A}\tilde{\mathbf{P}}_j\mathbf{C}_j'(\tilde{R} + \mathbf{C}_j\tilde{\mathbf{P}}_j\mathbf{C}_j')^{-1}\mathbf{C}_j\tilde{\mathbf{P}}_j\mathbf{A}'$$

3.2 QP Implementation

The Finite Horizon Optimal Control Problem (FHOCP) representing the PeMPC is defined as

$$U^o(k) = \arg \min_{u(k)} \mathcal{J}_j(x(k), u(\cdot), k) \quad (10)$$

where \mathcal{J}_j is the time-varying cost function (7) and $U^o(k) = [u^o(k) \ u^o(k+1) \ \dots \ u^o(k+N-1)]$ is the computed optimal control vector. Then according to the Receding Horizon principle, the FHOCP must be solved at each sample time k , but only the first element of the optimal control vector is applied. This optimization problem is subject to the hard and soft input constraints defined in Messori et al. (2015).

The FHOCP and the constraints have to be converted in the Quadratic Programming (QP) problem where the cost function is:

$$\mathcal{J}_j^{QP}(x(k), u(\cdot), k) = \frac{1}{2}U(k)'H_jU(k) + F_j'U(k)$$

with

$$H_j = \mathcal{B}_j'\mathcal{Q}_j\mathcal{B}_j + I_n$$

$$F_j' = (\mathcal{A}_j\mathbf{x}(k) + \mathcal{M}_jD(k) - Y^0(k))' \mathcal{Q}_j\mathcal{B}_j - U^0(k)'$$

where all the terms not depending on $U(k)$ have been omitted because they do not change the result of the optimization process, and where the vectors $U(k)$, $D(k)$, $Y^0(k)$ are defined as

$$U(k) = [u(k) \ u(k+1) \ \dots \ u(k+N-1)]'$$

$$Y^0(k) = [y^0(k+1) \ \dots \ y^0(k+N-1) \ 0 \ \dots \ 0]'$$

$$D(k) = [d(k) \ d(k+1) \ \dots \ d(k+N-1)]'$$

and by defining $j, h := \text{mod}(k+h, p)$, the matrices \mathcal{A}_j , \mathcal{B}_j , \mathcal{M}_j , \mathcal{Q}_j can be defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}_j &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{C}_{j,0}\mathbf{A} \\ \mathbf{C}_{j,1}\mathbf{A}^2 \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{C}_{j,N-2}\mathbf{A}^{N-1} \\ \mathbf{A}^N \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathcal{Q}_j = \begin{bmatrix} q & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & q & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & P_j \end{bmatrix} \\ \mathcal{B}_j &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{C}_{j,0}\mathbf{B} & 0 & \dots & \dots & 0 \\ \mathbf{C}_{j,1}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{B} & \mathbf{C}_{j,1}\mathbf{B} & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{C}_{j,N-2}\mathbf{A}^{N-2}\mathbf{B} & \dots & \dots & \mathbf{C}_{j,N-2}\mathbf{B} & 0 \\ \mathbf{A}^{N-1}\mathbf{B} & \dots & \dots & \mathbf{A}\mathbf{B} & \mathbf{B} \end{bmatrix} \\ \mathcal{M}_j &= \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{C}_{j,0}\mathbf{M} & 0 & \dots & \dots & 0 \\ \mathbf{C}_{j,1}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{M} & \mathbf{C}_{j,1}\mathbf{M} & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{C}_{j,N-2}\mathbf{A}^{N-2}\mathbf{M} & \dots & \dots & \mathbf{C}_{j,N-2}\mathbf{M} & 0 \\ \mathbf{A}^{N-1}\mathbf{M} & \dots & \dots & \mathbf{A}\mathbf{M} & \mathbf{M} \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned}$$

This optimization problem is then solved online by the *quadprog* function of Matlab[®].

4. SIMULATIONS & RESULTS

4.1 The UVA/Padova metabolic simulator

The proposed work was developed using the UVA/Padova simulator, a metabolic simulator approved by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) as an alternative to animal testing. This commercially available software is extensively used in the literature (Visentin et al. (2018)) for designing and testing AP control strategies, as well as safety modules (Visentin et al. (2014); Incremona et al. (2018); Man et al. (2014); Kovatchev et al. (2009)). It includes a compartmental model equipped with a population of 100 adult patients that are able to represent the metabolic behavior of the entire diabetic population. The latest version of the simulator also accounts for intraday variability, simulating glucose fluctuation in insulin sensitivity throughout the day for a realistic depiction of metabolic behavior. The datasets generated with the simulator involved an identification scenario (id-sc) to identify the DMP and PeMMP. The id-sc lasts 53 hours during which the patient is treated with six meals as follows: 30 [g] for each breakfast, 60 [g] and 70 [g] for the first and second lunch, respectively, and 80 [g] and 90 [g] for the first and second dinner, respectively. The control operates in open-loop mode for two hours starting from midnight and then the DMPC is applied. Another scenario was designed (test-sc-1) to test prediction performances of the models in which the patient consumed three meals (breakfast, lunch, and dinner) of 60 [g], 50 [g], and 70 [g], respectively and in which insulin is administered by a DMPC equipped with an Av model. Finally another realistic scenario spanning 30 days (test-sc-2) has been put in place to test control performances where each meal size and time has been extracted from a uniform random distribution. The selected parameters are: $7:30 \pm 30$ [min], 45 ± 25 [g] for the breakfast; $12:30 \pm 30$ [min], 60 ± 25 [g] for the lunch; $20:30 \pm 30$ [min], 75 ± 30 [g] for the dinner. All the simulations have been performed with the following parameters: \tilde{u} given by the basal-bolus therapy where the meal bolus is computed exploiting the patient's time varying carbohydrate ratio,

$\bar{y} = 115$ [mg/dl], $G_b = 120$ [mg/dl], $T_s = 15$ [min], $t_S^B = 5:00$, $t_S^L = 12:00$, $t_S^D = 19:00$ and $t_{switch} = 30$ [min] as in Toffanin et al. (2019).

4.2 Performance Metrics

Prediction performance was assessed using the FIT index, a normalized index that measures how closely the prediction matches the actual data. A FIT value of 100% indicates perfect prediction while 0% indicates that the model is a constant predictor, namely its prediction is equal to the known present value. It is formulated as follows

$$FIT = 100 \left(1 - \frac{\sum_{k=1}^N \|\hat{G}(k) - G(k)\|}{\sum_{k=1}^N \|G(k) - \bar{G}(k)\|} \right)$$

where \bar{G} is the mean of G , and $\|\cdot\|$ denotes the norm of the signal; N is the total number of samples of CGM data.

Control performance indexes have been selected following the consensus endpoints for AP trial described in Maahs et al. (2016) and Danne et al. (2017). They include the Mean BG (M), Standard Deviation (SD) and Coefficient of Variation (CV) of BG, the percentage of time spent in safe range [70, 180] [mg/dl] (T_r), the percentage of time spent in tight range [80, 140] [mg/dl] (T_{tr}), the percentage of time spent above 180 [mg/dl] (T_a), the percentage of time spent below 70 [mg/dl] (T_b) and the number of Hypo Treatments (HT) patient had to endure ($\#ht$). These metrics are computed during the overall day and night (O), during night (N, 0:00–8:00), and as an average of all the PostPrandial (PP) periods (4 [h]) of the whole simulation.

4.3 Identification Results

In this section, the prediction performances of the PeMMP are tested against those of the DMP. The results of the models predictions are shown in Fig. 2 where it is possible to see how the patient's glucose at the current time instant (black line) is estimated by the 1-hour glucose predictions of the DMP and PeMMP (green and purple, respectively). It is evident that the patient experiences severe hypoglycemia in the morning PP period, as the DMP fails to accurately and timely predict the incoming hypoglycemia, estimating a glucose of 93.2 [mg/dl] at 10:30, whereas the actual value was 37.8 [mg/dl]. This inaccurate prediction can be harmful for glucose regulation since the controller would inject excessive insulin underestimating its effect. In contrast, the PeMMP more accurately predicts future glucose, estimating a glucose of 53.0 [mg/dl] at 10:30, thereby improving upon the DMP's prediction. The PeMMP's more accurate predictions, and particularly its ability to foresee postprandial hypoglycemia, enhance glucose control, as reported in Section 4.3. For the overall prediction of the simulated scenario, the DMP achieves a FIT of 39.7%, while the PeMMP achieves a FIT of 81.9%.

4.4 Control Performance

In this Section control performances of a DMPC and the PeMPC are tested. The parameters used to assess control performances are: $q = 0.0076$ for both DMPC and PeMPC, chosen as in Patek et al. (2012) and $\hat{Q} = \text{blkdiag}(0.1 \cdot I_{n_f})$ for the DMPC and $\hat{Q} = \text{blkdiag}(0.01 \cdot I_{n_B}, 0.1 \cdot$

Fig. 2. 1-hour glucose predictions of the DMP and of the PeMMP on test-sc-1; it can be noted that the patient after breakfast experiences a severe hypoglycemia, the PeMMP is able to capture that behavior while the DMP completely misses it.

Table 1. Results obtained simulating the strategies DMPC and PeMPC with test-sc-2.

		Nominal scenario		
		O	N	PP
M [mg/dl]	DMPC	116.90	105.06	130.12
	PeMPC	118.28	105.12	130.31
SD [mg/dl]	DMPC	26.90	12.27	29.88
	PeMPC	23.14	12.19	25.66
CV [mg/dl]	DMPC	0.23	0.12	0.23
	PeMPC	0.20	0.12	0.20
T_r [%]	DMPC	95.43	98.94	93.45
	PeMPC	97.84	99.08	96.31
T_{tr} [%]	DMPC	76.23	96.66	59.06
	PeMPC	81.88	96.68	65.76
T_a [%]	DMPC	2.57	0.00	5.13
	PeMPC	1.85	0.00	3.69
T_b [%]	DMPC	2.00	1.06	1.42
	PeMPC	0.31	0.92	0.00
$\#ht$	DMPC	21.00	2.00	10.00
	PeMPC	2.00	1.00	0.00

$I_{n_L}, 0.1 \cdot I_{n_D}) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ for the PeMPC chosen with a trial and error procedure. Simulation results are reported in Table 1 and show how the use of PeMMP, which better captures time-varying dynamics of the patient, allows to achieve a robust and reliable control. The use of this new model is able to improve all performance indexes in particular it significantly reduces hypoglycemia experienced by the patients in the PP periods (T_b from 1.42% to 0.00%) while at the same time reducing T_a (from 5.13% to 3.69%) thus achieving a better glucose control (T_r from 93.45% to 96.31%, T_{tr} from 59.06% to 65.76%). Moreover the $\#ht$ index passes from 10 to 0 in the PP. This indicates that with the developed control strategy the patient has to treat himself much less often to avoid severe hypoglycemia. Fig. 3 shows the glucose dynamics of the patient undergoing test-sc-1 and controlled by the MPCs based on the two different models: the poor prediction performances of the DMP during the morning PP period lead to a severe hypoglycemia while the PeMMP enables the controller to maintain the patient in range avoiding hypoglycemia.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study highlights the efficacy of incorporating a PeMMP within the PeMPC for managing glucose vari-

Fig. 3. Comparison of glucose dynamics and insulin delivered by DMPC (violet) and PeMPC (green) with test-sc-1.

ability in individuals with T1D. By addressing the time-varying dynamics of insulin sensitivity through periodic modeling and smooth switching between models, the PeMMP significantly outperformed the conventional DMP in both predictive accuracy and control outcomes.

Simulation results carried out for one day showed that the PeMMP achieved a FIT index of 81.9%, substantially higher than the DMP's 39.7%, indicating much better alignment of predicted glucose with actual BG levels. Control performance improvements for a scenario spanning 30 days were evident with the PeMPC across all key metrics by increasing the time within safe and tight range, while reducing hyper and hypoglycemia events. Furthermore, the number of hypo treatments that the patient had to endure dropped significantly passing from 10 to 0 in PP periods, meaning that the developed approach greatly limits hypoglycemia and patient interventions.

These findings confirm the potential of a PeMPC to better regulate glucose regulation in T1D, offering a robust and adaptive framework capable of enhancing both safety and quality of life. The extension of this work to the whole 100 patient cohort is currently under study, future research will consider the robustness of the approach under changes in insulin sensitivity.

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